

One Vibration Too Many: When Music Merges Under Your Skin

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Abstract. Vibrotactile systems offer a promising route for musical accessibility, yet it remains unclear to what extent the tactile system can segregate simultaneous frequency components. We tested whether two sinusoidal vibrations delivered through a single actuator can be perceived as distinct. Participants judged whether they felt one or two components while frequency separation was systematically varied. Across conditions, two-component stimuli were rarely perceived as two distinct vibrations, suggesting that polyphonic content cannot be reliably conveyed through a single vibrating actuator.

Keywords: Tactile Segregation · Psychophysics

1 Introduction and Methodology

In audition, frequency separation can determine whether simultaneous components fuse or remain distinct [1]. Tones within one cochlear critical band are typically heard as a single sound [2]. To what extent tactile perception follows similar principles is unknown. We therefore tested whether frequency separation governs tactile segregation for two-component vibrations ($F1$ lower, $F2$ higher), distinguishing pairs above and below the octave boundary ($F2 = 2F1$; Fig. 1).

For $F2 \geq 2F1$, tactile sensitivity differences across frequency mean that subjective intensity-matched components can differ in displacement amplitude: Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles peak near 30 and 250 Hz [3], and thresholds fall by ~ 24 dB per octave between 20–280 Hz [4]. Higher frequencies thus require smaller amplitudes [5], producing a large $F1$ envelope (ENV) and a smaller $F2$ fine structure (FS). We predicted increasing segregation with $F2/F1$ (‘Grassy Hill’ stimuli).

For $F2 < 2F1$, physical interaction generates emergent frequencies: an envelope at $F2 - F1$ and a fine structure at $(F1 + F2)/2$, yielding a beat plus a buzz-like sensation. We predicted increasing segregation with FS/ENV (‘Beat’ stimuli).

Fifteen participants (12 female; mean age 25.5 ± 1.9 years) judged whether each stimulus contained one or two components. The set comprised 19 single-frequency and 45 dual-frequency stimuli (25 Grassy Hill, 20 Beat) spanning 2–350

Fig. 1: ‘Grassy Hill’ and ‘Beat’ stimuli with their envelope (ENV) and fine structure (FS) frequencies. Examples: 10+100 Hz and 100+110 Hz, plotted over 0.5s.

Hz. Each was presented three times in random order. Stimuli were equalised in perceived intensity and actuator sound was masked with white noise through noise cancelling headphones. The study was approved by the Commission Cantonale d’Ethique de la Recherche (CCER, Geneva).

2 Results and Discussion

Participants correctly identified single-frequency stimuli as a single component in 83.69% (SD = 12.93) of trials. For dual-frequency stimuli, the probability of perceiving two components increased systematically with FS/ENV ratio (Fig. 2). Each doubling of the separation ratio increased double-response rates by 21.53% (95% CI: 17.36–25.70, $p = 3.24 \times 10^{-13}$; $R^2 = 0.721$).

Beat stimuli elicited higher double-response rates than Grassy Hill stimuli, with a fixed offset of 10.53% ($\beta = 10.53$, $p = 0.013$), corresponding to a consistent 10% increase in double-vibration reports. Random effects indicated substantial participant variability. Many stimuli were either perceived as a single component or produced responses at chance level (grey region in Fig. 2), with relatively few stimuli yielding reliable two-component percepts.

The overall low rate of perceptual segregation indicates that single-actuator devices have limited capacity for conveying polyphonic musical content. Our model suggests that a dual percept requires an exceptionally large separation between the ENV and FS temporal components. Such separations are rare in musical contexts; melodic note spacing in Western tonal music typically spans two to three octaves [6, 7], equating to a separation ratio of up to around 8. ‘Beat’ stimuli offered only a modest advantage, and only at large FS/ENV ratios. Future work may test whether spatially separating components improves segregation.

Fig. 2: Two-component percepts versus FS/ENV separation with means \pm SE and model fits. Grey region marks chance-level responses.

Interdisciplinary Exchange We invite researchers to discuss feature extraction by receptors (real or simulated) of complex waveforms.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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